

GUIDED WAVES IN A MULTILAYERED COMPOSITE AND ULTRASONIC NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

Analysis of wave propagation in a laminated composite plate with many layers is made difficult by the anisotropy of the laminae, different lay-ups, many layers and defects in the fabricated plate. A good understanding of the wave field in such a plate without defects is a prerequisite for use of ultrasonic techniques to evaluate the various defects that can substantially reduce the strength and service life of this structure. In this paper we present results of modeling studies of wave propagation and scattering in a multilayered composite plate. The analysis technique combines the finite element discretization through the thickness with wave form representation along the plate in order to calculate the dispersive modes of propagation in the plate. To study scattering of these waves by a matrix crack that grows into delaminations we have used a hybrid finite element representation of the field near the crack and the modal representation of the scattered exterior field. Results are presented showing the dependence of the reflection and transmission coefficients on the size of the crack with delamination which can be used to size the defect using ultrasonic techniques.

KEYWORDS: Laminated/Composite/Plate; Cracks/Delaminations; Scattering; Ultrasonic/Nondestructive/Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the low density, high performance and increased service life, composite materials are receiving wide attention in aerospace industry and in many other commercial applications. Therefore, analysis of wave propagation in laminated composite plates

is of current interest among many researchers. A comprehensive knowledge of wave scattering plays an important role in identifying defects and material degradation. Recently, it has been demonstrated by Spetzler and Datta (1) that inspection of cracks in plates can be carried out using Rayleigh-Lamb waves detected by capacitive transducer. The present theoretical study of diffraction of plane strain waves by a normal central matrix crack in a laminated composite plate has been motivated by these experimental findings.

Many references on earlier work on problems of wave diffraction by cracks can be found in the review article by Miklowitz (2). Datta, *et al.* (3) is a good source of references to current work on wave diffraction by cracks. Rokhlin (4,5) has analyzed the scattering of Lamb waves by an infinitely thin crack parallel to the surface of an isotropic plate using the modified Wiener-Hopf technique and the method of multiple diffractions. Tan and Auld (6) investigated scattering of Lamb waves by an infinitely thin crack normal to the surface of an isotropic plate using the normal mode variational method. However, application of these methods is extremely difficult if not impossible for cracks of arbitrary shape. Abduljabbar, *et al.* (7) presented a hybrid method useful for the analysis of the scattering of horizontally polarized shear (SH) waves by arbitrarily shaped cracks in isotropic plates. Later, Koshiha, *et al.* (8) extended this approach to Lamb wave scattering by cracks in isotropic plates. Recently, Paskaramoorthy, *et al.* (9) and Al-Nassar (10) used this hybrid method to investigate scattering of waves by cracks and weldment in an isotropic plate. Information on wave scattering by cracks in anisotropic and laminated plates is however very limited. Only recently Bratton, *et al.* (11) and Karunasena, *et al.* (12) have presented results for scattering by normal surface breaking cracks in uniaxial and cross-ply fiber-reinforced plates. Also, Ju, *et al.* (13) have studied scattering by a delamination in a uniaxial fiber-reinforced plate using a different technique that combines finite elements and Green's function integral representations.

In this paper we have used the method used in (11) and (12) to study scattering by a centrally located normal matrix crack in a cross-ply fiber-reinforced plate. Numerical results for reflection and transmission coefficients for propagating symmetric and anti-symmetric guided waves show interesting effects of varying crack lengths. Of particular interest are the results showing the dependence of these coefficients on the extent of delamination into which the central crack grows when it meets the adjacent laminae with 0° fiber orientation. The results have potential applications in ultrasonic non-destructive evaluation (NDE).

2. FORMULATION

Time harmonic elastic wave propagation in an infinite plate composed of perfectly bonded layers with possibly distinct mechanical properties and thickness is considered. The two faces of the plate $z = 0$ and $z = 2H$ are traction free and the global rectangular cartesian coordinate system x, y, z is defined in Fig. 1. The direction of wave

Figure 1. Geometry of the layered plate and the crack extending to delamination (shown by solid and dashed lines)

propagation is x . The central crack is located in the interior regions bounded by the vertical boundaries B^+ and B^- at $x = x^+$ and $x = x^-$, respectively, as shown.

2.1 Wave Functions for the Exterior Regions In the exterior regions R^+ and R^- , the total wave field consists of a scattered field and the incident field. The scattered field is represented by wave functions expansion. Details of the methodology used to obtain wave functions for a laminated plate can be found in Karunasena, *et al.* (14). Only a brief outline is given here. In this method, each layer is divided into several sublayers so that total number of sublayers through the thickness $2H$ is N . For simplicity in analysis, each layer is assumed to be transversely isotropic with the symmetry axis making an arbitrary angle with the x -axis. This assumption of transverse isotropy is not necessary for the development of the equations, but it is made here to keep the algebra simple. Let u, v, w denote displacement components in x, y, z directions, respectively. Consider the i th sublayer bounded by $z = z_i$ and $z = z_{i+1}$. Within the i th sublayer we choose a local rectangular cartesian coordinate system X, Y, Z with the origin at the midplane, X -axis along the symmetry direction (fiber direction), Z -axis vertically down, and Y -axis in the horizontal plane. The stress-strain relation within this sublayer in the local X, Y, Z coordinate system is given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{XX} \\ \sigma_{YY} \\ \sigma_{ZZ} \\ \sigma_{YZ} \\ \sigma_{ZX} \\ \sigma_{XY} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{XX} \\ \epsilon_{YY} \\ \epsilon_{ZZ} \\ \gamma_{YZ} \\ \gamma_{ZX} \\ \gamma_{XY} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{IJ} and ϵ_{IJ} are the stress and strain components respectively, and $\gamma_{IJ} = 2\epsilon_{IJ}$. C_{IJ} are the elements of constitutive matrix for the sublayer. Note that $C_{22} = C_{33}$, $C_{55} = C_{66}$, $C_{12} = C_{13}$, and $C_{44} = (C_{22} - C_{23})/2$. Let ϕ be the angle between the global x -axis and the local X -axis measured anticlockwise from the global x -axis. The stress and strain components for the i th sublayer in the global x, y, z coordinate system are related by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{zx} \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} & 0 & 0 & D_{16} \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{23} & 0 & 0 & D_{26} \\ D_{13} & D_{23} & D_{33} & 0 & 0 & D_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{44} & D_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{45} & D_{55} & 0 \\ D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{36} & 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{zx} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where D_{ij} are related to C_{IJ} by the equations given in Appendix A of Karunasena *et al.* (15).

Using the interpolation polynomial in the z -direction, the displacement components are approximated as

$$\{U\} = [N]\{q\} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\{U\}^T = [u_x \quad u_y \quad u_z] \quad (4a)$$

$$\{q\}^T = [u_x^b \quad u_y^b \quad u_z^b \quad u_x^m \quad u_y^m \quad u_z^m \quad u_x^f \quad u_y^f \quad u_z^f] \quad (4b)$$

$$[N] = \begin{bmatrix} n_1 & 0 & 0 & n_2 & 0 & 0 & n_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & n_1 & 0 & 0 & n_2 & 0 & 0 & n_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & n_1 & 0 & 0 & n_2 & 0 & 0 & n_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4c)$$

In Eq. (4b) the generalized displacements \mathbf{u}^b , \mathbf{u}^m , and \mathbf{u}^f are evaluated at the back, middle, and front nodal surfaces of the sublayer. The interpolation polynomials n_1 , n_2 , and n_3 are quadratic functions given by

$$\begin{aligned} n_1 &= -\hat{z} + 2\hat{z}^2 \\ n_2 &= 1 - 4\hat{z}^2 \\ n_3 &= 2\hat{z}^2 + \hat{z} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{z} = z/h$, h being the thickness of the sublayer.

Using Hamilton's principle, the governing equation for the entire plate is found to be

$$[K_1]\{Q\}'' + [K_2^*]\{Q\}' - [K_3]\{Q\} - [M]\{\ddot{Q}\} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Here $[K_1]$, $[K_3]$, and $[M]$ are symmetric and $[K_2^*]$ is skew symmetric. Primes and dots denote differentiation with respect to x and t , respectively. (Q) is the vector of all nodal displacements. For wave propagation in the x -direction (Q) is assumed to be of the form

$$\{Q\} = \{Q_0\}e^{j(kx - \omega t)} \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eq. (7) in Eq. (6) we obtain the eigenvalue problem

$$[-K_1k^2 + K_2^*jk - K_3 + M\omega^2]\{Q_0\} = 0 \quad (8)$$

For nontrivial solution (Q_0) the determinant of the matrix formed by the square brackets in the above equation must be zero. This equation can be solved to find ω for a given k or to find k when ω is known.

It may be noted that the wave functions and the dispersion relation between the frequency and wavenumber can be obtained analytically also. However, for a multilayered plate the dispersion equation is rather complex so that the solutions for the wavenumbers at any given frequency are difficult to obtain. To alleviate this difficulty approximate roots obtained using the stiffness method described above are used as initial estimates of the exact solutions and then Muller's method as given in Conte and Boor (16) is used to solve the exact dispersion equation. Once the exact wavenumbers, $k = k_m (m = 1, 2, \dots)$, are determined, the wave functions (mode shapes) for displacements and stresses can be computed as vectors at successive interfaces between sublayers. It should be noted at this stage that division into sublayers is not required to obtain the exact dispersion relation but is used to compute the values of wave functions at sublayer interfaces. If the problem under consideration is symmetric or antisymmetric only half thickness of the plate can be modeled using appropriate boundary conditions at the middle plane of the plate.

Consider the case in which the incident wave is the p th propagating mode corresponding to the wave number k_p . After striking the crack at $x = 0$, a scattered wave field will be generated. This can be expressed at the nodes on the boundary B^+ as

$$\mathbf{q}_B^{s+} = \mathbf{G}^+ \mathbf{D}^+, \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathbf{G}^+ = [\mathbf{q}_1 \quad \mathbf{q}_2 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{q}_m \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{q}_M], \quad (10a)$$

$$\mathbf{D}^{+T} = \langle D_1^+ \quad D_2^+ \quad \dots \quad D_m^+ \quad \dots \quad D_M^+ \rangle, \quad (10b)$$

$$D_m^+ = A_m^+ \exp(jk_m x^+), \quad m = 1 \text{ to } M. \quad (10c)$$

Note that \mathbf{G}^+ is a matrix of size $2(N+1)$ by M . The nodal force vector at the boundary B^+ due to scattered field can be formed as (see Karunasena, *et al.* (17))

$$\mathbf{p}_B^{s+} = \mathbf{F}^+ \mathbf{D}^+, \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{F}^+ is the matrix of nodal force vectors at the interfaces due to normalized stress components σ_{xx} and σ_{xz} . \mathbf{F}^+ is a rectangular matrix of size $2(N + 1)$ by M . In constructing the force vector, the consistent load vector formulation given in Bathe (18) has been used. Following a similar procedure at the boundary B^- , we obtain the displacement and force vectors due to scattered field as

$$\mathbf{q}_B^{s-} = \mathbf{G}^- \mathbf{D}^-, \quad (12a)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_B^{s-} = \mathbf{G}^- \mathbf{D}^-, \quad (12b)$$

respectively. In a similar manner the boundary displacement and force vectors for the incident wave can be constructed.

2.2 Solution to the Scattering Problem To solve the scattering problem the interior region R is modeled by finite elements. The crack tip singularity is modeled using six node quarterpoint triangular crack tip elements proposed by Barsoum (19). The crack tip elements are surrounded by a layer of transition elements followed by conventional four node elements. The layers adjacent to the vertical boundaries B^+ and B^- consist of five node elements with the middle node lying on the boundaries. This is done to increase the number of nodes lying on the boundaries. The global solution is obtained by imposing the continuity of total (incident plus scattered) displacements and traction conditions on the boundaries B^+ and B^- . These lead to linear algebraic equations governing the coefficients A_m^+ and A_m^- .

We define the reflection coefficient R_{pm} of the m th reflected mode and transmission coefficient T_{pm} of the m th transmitted mode due to p th incident mode propagating in the negative x -direction as,

$$R_{pm} = \frac{A_m^+}{A_p^{\text{in}}}, \quad (13a)$$

$$T_{pm} = \begin{cases} \frac{A_m^-}{A_p^{\text{in}}}, & m \neq p \\ \frac{A_p^{\text{in}} + A_m^-}{A_p^{\text{in}}}, & m = p \end{cases} \quad (13b)$$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The methods described above were used to obtain the wavenumbers for the guided modes (propagating, nonpropagating and evanescent) and subsequently the reflection and transmission coefficients of the scattered modes. The example plate considered was an 8-layer $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s^4$ continuous graphite fiber reinforced epoxy matrix cross-ply

composite. The material properties are listed in Table 1. The following nondimensionalization has been used for the frequency and wavenumber.

$$\Omega = \frac{\omega H}{\sqrt{(C_{55}/\zeta)_{0^\circ}}}, \quad \gamma = kH$$

TABLE 1 Elastic Stiffnesses of the 0° and 90° Laminae in Units of 10^2 GPa

Layer	$\zeta(Mg/m^3)$	C_{11}	C_{22}	C_{12}	C_{44}	C_{55}
0° Lamina	1.8	1.6073	0.1392	0.0644	0.0350	0.0707
90° Lamina	1.8	0.1392	1.6073	0.0644	0.0707	0.0350

Figures 2 and 3 show the changes in the magnitudes of reflection and transmission coefficients $|T_{2n}|$ and $|R_{2n}|$ ($n = 1, 2, 3$) when the incident mode was the 2nd symmetric mode. Ω was chosen to be 4. Note that because of the symmetry a scattered field would consist only of symmetric modes. At the frequency considered there were 3 symmetric and 3 antisymmetric propagating modes. 21 modes were used in the wave function expansion of the scattered field. These figures show that reflection and transmission coefficients of the scattered second mode are the most sensitive to the crack length and those of the third mode are the least affected by the crack. $|T_{2n}|$ and $|R_{2n}|$ ($n = 1, 2$) change gradually until the crack is about half way through the thickness of the middle laminae. Then $|T_{22}|$ and $|R_{22}|$ change quite rapidly as the crack is almost all the way through. Then as the crack grows into delaminations at the interfaces between the middle (90°) and adjacent (0°) laminae these coefficients change less rapidly in a linear manner. $|T_{21}|$ and $|R_{21}|$, on the other hand, tend to decrease reaching a plateau as the delaminations become h in length. It was found (but not shown here) that the third incident mode ($p = 3$) was not affected much by the crack. The first incident mode ($p = 1$) $|T_{12}|$ and $|R_{12}|$ were found to behave similarly as $|T_{21}|$ and $|R_{21}|$. This is expected from the reciprocity relations between the pairs (T_{pn}, T_{np}) and (R_{pn}, R_{np}) established in (12).

Figures 4 and 5 show the behaviors of $|T_{1n}|$ and $|R_{1n}|$ ($n = 1, 2, 3$), for the first antisymmetric incident mode. In the case of antisymmetric incident modes it was found that they were not sensitive to the normal central crack even when it was almost all the way through the thickness of the middle layers. However, as the extent of delamination grew they all changed abruptly. The coefficients $|T_{11}|$ and $|R_{11}|$ showed the most sensitivity to the increasing length of delaminations as seen from Figs. 4 and 5.

Figure 3. $|R_{2n}|$ vs a/h

* Note that $c = 0$ until b is equal to h

Figure 5 $|R_{1n}|$ vs a/h

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